

**ON THE PERSONAL PSYCHOLOGICAL PROTECTION MECHANISM IN
EXTREME SITUATIONS
SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS.**

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Annotation: The article talks about the specific features of the psychological protection mechanism observed in the individual in extreme situations, and highlights the important aspects of the psychological conditions manifested in the activities of individuals in extreme situations.

Key words: Affect, frustration, stereotype, apathy, aggression, estruction, autoaggression, regression, asthenia, somatic.

Аннотация: В статье говорится об особенностях механизма психологической защиты, наблюдаемых у личности в экстремальных ситуациях, и освещаются важные аспекты психологических состояний, проявляющихся в деятельности личности в экстремальных ситуациях.

Ключевые слова: Аффект, фрустрация, стереотип, апатия, агрессия, эструкция, аутоагрессия, регрессия, астения, соматика.

Specific types of mental states observed in a person in extreme situations. There are many types of extreme cases. Some of them were considered as applied to specific situations. However, apart from them, there are specific types of extreme situations that disrupt human activity. In addition to stress, we can include affect, frustration, fear and psychological crisis in such cases.

Affect (frenzy) - in Latin, mental excitement is understood as a strong and short excited state of unruly character.

Physiological affect is an excited state that does not go beyond the limits of norms, it is characterized by sudden appearance, great strength and short duration. In order to develop the psychological criteria of physiological affect, it is necessary to determine the characteristics of situations depending on its occurrence and the internal structure of the excited state. As a rule, such an affect appears when the subject continues to work and encounters insurmountable obstacles. Its condition can develop in tense conditions of time when a person makes a decision about the nature of their next actions in a complex emotional situation and implements this decision in a practical way. The conflict between the need to act and the possibility of finding exactly the same way out of the given situation leads to the appearance of hysteria.

Such a situation is very important for human activity in extreme conditions.

"Emotional states, as well as lack of behavioral preprogramming, result in the manifestation of a strong affective response. Then the influencer's power is determined primarily by the meaning of personality in the situation in which the person acted. Even a minor cause can produce a short-term thought as a result of experiencing frenzy under the circumstances of an injured state."

However, it is not determined by the mechanism of emergence of excitement in a psychological situation, and it is primarily expressed in the change of consciousness, human activity. In a state of excitement, there is a narrowing of consciousness: attention is focused on experiencing frenzy and imaginings associated with the traumatic situation, the completeness of the reflection of the situation decreases, self-control decreases, actions become stereotyped (patterned). They obey emotions and not logical thinking. The course of frenzy is usually characterized by external activity, tense facial expressions and other expressive movements, gestures.

In an extreme situation, fear is one of the external activities of the affect. Fear arises in the inability of a person to overcome the sudden appearance of a very dangerous situation. A feeling of fear can overwhelm a person, suppress his mind and will, and paralyze his ability to act and fight. A person freezes, passively waits for his fate and flees "in the direction of his head". After a frenzy, a person always does not remember the details of his behavior and situation, feels tired and sad.

A person who falls into a frenzy can leave by using his will. The more a person's willpower is developed, the less he is prone to madness, or does not allow it at all. Distraction and distraction are also important in reducing or preventing tantrums. Psychologists say that people who are "burning" are advised to count to one hundred in a nervous state or to start something slowly: sawing, raking, digging and engaging in other work. Then the mind is freed from the "occupation" of excitement, and a person begins to report to himself about the management of his state and behavior.

In extreme conditions, frustration (Latin frustration-false, mood disorder) can also occur. Frustration is a mental state or expression of growing internal psychic tension, a psychological affect associated with failure to achieve a goal, disappointment. Frustration occurs in the following processes:

- 1) Strong reasoning in achieving the goal (satisfaction of students).
- 2) In achieving the goal with insurmountable difficulties.

The external activity of frustration is experiencing failures, disappointment, tension. Experiences vary depending on the situation: guilt, agitation, and suppressed anger. The depth of frustration depends on the strength (amount) of the frustrator, the usual forms of exposure to obstacles, the use of skills and experience to overcome life's difficulties, and the frustration tolerance.

The following types of frustrating behavior are usually distinguished:

- a) motor stimulation is expressed in purposeless and irregular influences:
- b) apathy;
- c) aggression (aggression) and destruction, autoaggression (against oneself)
- g) regression, which is understood as an appeal to dominant behavior in very similar situations, is a decrease in its structure.

The transfer of a difficult situation to a situation of frustration is carried out in two directions - along the line of loss of control by the mind, that is, the loss of "reason-for-purpose" behavior."

Frustration is usually considered as a harmful phenomenon for a person. As a rule of thumb, the pressure called by frustration is said to be the fact that it can serve to focus on a specific cause and to achieve a goal.

If cheating does not lead to a constructive way out of the situation, the pressure will continue to build. As a result, its result reaches a level that does not allow successful activities aimed at achieving the goal, and has the character of decay. All of this is consistent with the Erks-Dodson law discussed earlier.

The consequences of frustration can be short-term and long-lasting. Overcoming it involves the use of autogenic methods of training to remove emotional-volitional tension, de-escalation of the conflict situation, friendly communication, distraction from the causes of frustration, and transfer of attention. In individuals with a strong nervous system, this condition is, as a rule, often expressed only in long-lasting and strong exposure to failures, that is, in the desire to prove that the observed failures of a person are sudden, in individuals with a weak nervous system, the state of frustration is not great. appears in failures and is known as asthenia and can stop work. Therefore, they need encouragement, detailed discussion of the reasons for failure and ways to eliminate them, setting goals that are clear and fully achievable in given situations.

A person experiences a psychological crisis several times during his life. They distinguish different types of crises related to their causes, for example, sudden change of work, change of profession, separation from family, retirement, change of social status. It is also possible to distinguish age-related crises "on somatic grounds (disease), social-status (role), internal growth.

Crises are an inseparable component of human life and activity. In psychology, they are seen as a necessary factor of personality development. For example, one of the founders of humanitarian psychology. R. May believes that it is impossible, and even unnecessary, to have a limited personality of a person. Therefore, a person should be ready to overcome the inevitable crises in his life, he should develop the appropriate direction in himself. Here, a lot depends on a person's personal qualities, his readiness to overcome various extreme situations.

Drawing a conclusion from the above, it should be noted that from the point of view of psychologists, crises are inevitable in human life, each of them has negative and positive components. The successful resolution of the crisis is progress in the development of the individual, possible personal growth. Failure to resolve the conflict is dangerous for the individual.

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